

HUMAN SEXUALITY, RELIGIONS AND RELIGIOUS FREEDOM: AREAS OF CONTENTIONS & INTERSECTIONS

GANOUNE DIOP¹

Human sexuality, religions and religious freedoms intersect at the confluence of human identity. This is the reason why the issue we are considering is so complex. Human beings are irreducible to one or several aspects or even the sum of characteristics of their persons. Human beings are not just biological beings, there is always more to human beings than what can be measured. Human beings are mysteries, rich and profound. The value of everyone is infinite. This is connected to human dignity. There is always more to anyone.

Regarding human sexuality, in our contemporary world, the current debate in the international community tends to focus almost exclusively on issues related to the legitimacy or non-legitimacy of the LGBTIQ claims to their rights. The meeting of experts has addressed the larger issues of sexuality which include, not only women's sexuality from the angle of all harmful practices such as female genital mutilations for example, but also male sexuality, and the harmful alpha male culture which distorts male self-image and lead to the instrumentalization of women robbing them of their human dignity. The deep and irreconcilable differences of various understandings of biblical texts on human sexuality, and marriage, are here to stay.

An overview of the landscape of opinions regarding same-sex marriage shows not only the differences between religious peoples and their various faith-based traditions but also among non-religiously affiliated persons. Most of the religious world claiming monotheistic faiths prohibits same sex marriages (Roman Catholic Church, Ecumenical Patriarchate, Russian and all Orthodox autocephalous churches, Assemblies of God, Islam, Orthodox Jewish Movement, Lutheran Church-Missouri Synod, American Baptist Churches, National Baptist Convention, Southern Baptist Convention). Some religious and philosophical traditions do not have statements about a unified position. These are Hinduism and Buddhism among other Asian traditions.

¹ Ganoune Diop, PhD, is Secretary General of the International Religious Liberty Association and Director of Public Affairs and Religious Liberty for the Seventh-day Adventist Church's World Headquarters. He also serves as Secretary of the Conference of Secretaries of Christian World Communions.

Despite the differences of beliefs at the root of our understanding of what it means to be a human being, a critical consensus is needed to stop the violence against people who disagree with others' anthropology. The foundational issue is an anthropological one and whether this anthropology is informed by how one understands biblical revelation as related to God's absolute will regarding creation and those God created in God's image. The complexity of the issue of human sexuality is therefore a theological issue. How one views God and God's purpose for creation, is going to inform how one relates to other human beings. Our conviction and commitment to God will affect our relationships with other human beings.

Need this understanding of God's ultimate will lead to violence against people who hold opposing views? That is the incontrovertible question to address. My church tradition has unequivocal statements regarding human sexuality. It also has statements about the integrity of the human person. An integrity that needs to remain inviolable whether it be physical, mental, spiritual, or social-cultural. The impulse to subjugate people with different lifestyles is present in religious contexts, where some use languages to criminalize, and demonize LGBTIQ. From criminalization to physical violence, the gap is easily bridged. Furthermore, as is the case in some countries, even the capital punishment is not spared for people who do not fit in the endorsed biblical norm of human sexuality. This area of competence is not that of religious people. Separation of religion and state can function as a deterrent against religious leaders taking the initiative to criminalize, discriminate, persecute, or execute those who dissent from their religious norms.

When it comes to religious freedom, it may be useful to mention that "Freedom of religion or belief is a universal fundamental human right inscribed in the UDHR." It is central to all the other freedoms. It is a compound freedom which presupposes the freedom of thought, of conscience, of religion, of choice, of expression, of association and of assembly. It is the freedom to profess, to practice, to propagate one's faith, to pass it on to one's children without restriction from the state or threat from popular hostility. It is the freedom to wear symbols, and to own properties where one can freely assemble with like-minded persons, to worship to simply to celebrate what one values.

The intersection of freedom of religion or belief and human sexuality is worth exploring more carefully. Human sexuality is an area where untold human suffering has taken place. Excruciating pain and senseless violence have been perpetrated against human beings based on their sexual orientation or identity. Both religions and atheistic ideologies have contributed to marginalizing, persecuting, and even murdering sexual minorities.

Unacceptable suffering, discrimination, inflicted pain, and murders against those who identify themselves as LGBTIQ have punctuated the history of the world. The perception of homosexuality as harmful led the Emperor Theodosius I to command that all passive homosexuals to be burned at the stake. According to the code of Theodosius (Theodosius II, 438), the passive role associated with femininity was a threat to the empire.²

Homosexuals have been considered scapegoats responsible for the tragedies that afflict society. In Europe they have been accused of bringing the black death (1348-1350) which decimated one third of the European population. The last condemnation of a homosexual to death occurred on October 10, 1783. In the US the last execution of a homosexual for being a homosexual occurred in South Carolina in 1873.

Coercion and violence against people who believe differently about themselves, and human sexuality is never legitimately justified. The differences of opinions on human sexuality have been and still is a platform where unjustified and unwarranted violence is perpetrated against minorities in the name of mere stubborn refusal to others to choose or embrace the identity of their choosing, however they have come to their conviction.

Violence in all its forms, whether physical or verbal. Violence against anyone is a violation of not only physical integrity but also human dignity. No person should be violated, abused, and deprived of their right to safety, and security. All persons are entitled to their physical, emotional and mental integrity.

The world has come a long way from witch hunt, gay bashing in the public square to more contained attitudes towards gender issues and sexual identity. The debate in the past few years and the report among Anglicans is illustrative of where a Christian tradition is in its engagements with rights. Most so-called Western nations have moved from a debate on the rights of LGBTI. The issue is no longer at least in most parts of the world, whether LGBTI persons should live or not but the focus is rather on their civil rights such as the right to marry. Same sex marriage is taboo in most part of the world. Nonetheless, justifications for harming a person because of their sexual orientation or identity is rejected in most part of the world.

The revisiting and the careful rethinking about the interrelatedness and interdependency and indivisibility of human rights and their foundation, human dignity, which I venture to call a moral imperative, have become urgent in light of the deep differences of opinions in reference to human sexuality, both in secular society and in the religious world. An incontrovertible or inescapable question comes to the fore in the context of this reflection on human sexuality and gender identity. Can people of same sex orientations be denied the

² Daniel Borrillo, *L'homophobie. Que sais-je* (Paris: Presse universitaire de France, 2000), 41.

prerogatives intrinsic to their human dignity, the so-called daughters' rights of human dignity? Explicitly, the right to personality, the right to dignified human subsistence, the right to reputation, the right to family life, the right to equality, the right to freedom of expression, the right to freedom of conscience and religion, the right to freedom of movement, the right to education, the right to employment and the right to due process?³

There can be no turning back or rewinding of the clock of history. Unless the state proves a person's mental or illness, and the sickness of harming oneself and society in self-mutilation for example, freedom of conscience or belief is for all. To the state is given the responsibility to regulate the security of citizens from harm and danger, not to individual opinions. Christian communions or traditions will continue to wrestle with their internal differences of interpretations and opinions regarding norms for human sexuality. That is part of being a communion where no one is forced to stay; but where dialogue can take place because of a common core embraced by all.

Let the conversation then continue, especially at a platform such as this one, a meeting of experts or even in larger contexts such as the United Nations, or in national debates where a consensus on what is human and humane, what are the rights and what is right for all are sought to hold together the human family.

- The differences of opinion among the Christian churches is here to stay. People interpret their holy texts differently. Seven biblical texts unambiguously condemn same sex practices. Nevertheless, people reading the same scriptures find some statements opaque and ancient culture bound. They claim the right to read differently.
- The right to choose one's identity is an inalienable right without which the foundation for human experience of freedom collapses. If all human rights are interrelated, interdependent and indivisible, then depriving any minority and any segment of the human family of any right would ultimately consists in negating their right to self-determination and therefore a denial of the very foundations of their humanity. The freedom to choose to define one's own identity according to one's own conscience and convictions, should be secured as the prerogative of every human being. The state is obviously called to be vigilant so that rights may not be instrumentalized to drift into trivialized human dignity.

Moreover, the very foundations of the Christian faith based on the freedom to choose to enter a covenant would be eroded or implode if this right is not enjoyed by every human being. Self-ownership and self-determination

3 Aharon Barak, *Human Dignity: The Constitutional Value and the Constitutional Right* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 288-301.

whether collectively or individually is a condition sine qua non if humankind is to assume its destiny and dignity. There are inevitable differences of opinions and of interpretations. But they need not lead to the devaluation of one's deeply held convictions or to violence towards those who believe differently about their sexual identity. Criminization belongs to the political and judicial spheres. Therefore, sentencing and punishing are not part of the ecclesiastical responsibility. Separation of religion and state is a deterrent against crossing the boundaries of one's jurisdictions.

CONCLUSION

In contemporary pluralistic societies opinions vary about almost every issue. The subject of human sexuality is no exception to this general rule. Christian churches are part of this contemporary phenomenon. The staggering diversity of opinions among churches and in every single tradition itself is a sign for the need of a platform which promotes the protection of the people's right to embrace the identity of their choice without being discriminated, intimidated, harassed, persecuted, harmed or murdered. This can be done without endorsing peoples' opinions, choices, and lifestyles.

Social peace, however, is too serious to be left to the regulations of religious beliefs alone. The public space benefits from secular neutral framework that allows people of various opinions to co-exist in the respect of their differences. Dialogue in the dignity of difference is called for by the imperative of freedom of conscience. A normative consensus about the ban of violence against people of various sexual orientations or identities should be promoted and may become a key factor in helping the human family move forward beyond conflict and fighting, to building respect and solidarity within the human family. Freedom from fear, freedom from being harassed, humiliated, or harmed should be the prerogative of every human person.

An incontrovertible or inescapable question comes to the fore in the context of this meeting of experts. Can people of same sex orientations be denied the prerogatives intrinsic to their human dignity, the so-called daughters' rights of human dignity? Explicitly, the right to personality, the right to dignified human subsistence, the right to reputation, the right to family life, the right to equality, the right to freedom of expression, the right to freedom of conscience and religion, the right to freedom of movement, the right to education, the right to employment and the right to due process.⁴ Christian communions or traditions and world religions will continue to wrestle with their internal

⁴ Aharon Barak, *Human Dignity: The Constitutional Value and the Constitutional Right* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 288-301.

differences of interpretations and opinions regarding norms for human sexuality. That is part of being a communion where no one is forced to stay; but where dialogue can take place because of a common core embraced by all. Compromising one's own beliefs would mean loss of one's identity. That need not be negotiable. But the value of respecting other peoples' humanity and choices without having to endorse their choices or lifestyle, is a moral imperative. Our common humanity calls for sharing the civil space in civility, and peaceful coexistence. This requires not compromise but negotiated accommodations.

Let the conversation then continue, especially at a platform such as the meeting of experts, and at other platforms where consensuses on what is human and humane, what are the rights and what is right for all are sought to hold together the human family in peaceful coexistence in the dignity of difference.

The human family can indeed choose the path of freedom, that is the solution to the dysfunction and disease of internalized dominance, the silly pride of thinking of oneself as superior to others based on belief on one's manifest destiny, exceptionalism, and election to privileges. The path to freedom would equally erode the foundations for social, cultural, economic matrixes of dominations. It would reconfigure the whole ecosystem of human experience from what is normative from what is fashionable and temporarily caught in the fleeting moments of one's arbitrary preferences. Freedom would also contribute to save us from the dreams of dominions which have even put people to burn at the stake. Michel Servette paid a price for opposing Calvin's vision of the city of God, a city upon the hill. The city is certainly not and maybe it can be said it will never be the kingdom of which Jesus said is not of this world.

All these words are based on the root "dom." Human dignity can function as a reminder and a deterrent which resists any attempt to being complicit to the practice of dominating human beings, reduced to domains to be domesticated, used, and disposed of. Humans after all are created in the image of God, it is believed. Let therefore God be honored in our showing solidarity, respect, and love of neighbors. Love is not predicated on agreeing or having the same opinions or beliefs, or votes. After all, as the Apostle Paul puts it, "while we were sinners, impious, enemies, God demonstrated God's love to us" (See Romans 5:6-11). The objects of God's love have infinite value, measured from the depth of God's love.

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